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Revision of the genus *Paraphamartania* Engel with description of two new species and comments on the related Nearctic genus *Cophura* Osten Sacken (Diptera: Asilidae)

Revisión del género *Paraphamartania* Engel con la descripción de dos nuevas especies y comentarios sobre el género neártico emparentado *Cophura* Osten Sacken (Diptera: Asilidae)

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ABSTRACT: Specimens of two undescribed species of *Paraphamartania* Engel, 1930, were collected in Spain and Portugal in 2014 and 2015. Both new species are closely related but can easily be differentiated by characters of the wings, sternites, genitalia and genetics. It became clear that some important generic characters of *Paraphamartania* such as the spines on the tip of midtibiae, have been overlooked by previous authors and the current definition of this genus is not complete.

A comparative study of *Paraphamartania*, *Aphamartania* Schiner, 1866 and *Cophura* Osten Sacken, 1887 showed that *Paraphamartania* is similar to the Nearctic genus *Cophura* and no clear characters besides geography are found to discriminate both genera. In contrast, *Paraphamartania* and *Cophura* are both easily distinguished from *Aphamartania* and from all other genera in the subfamily Brachyrhopalinae (sensu DIKOW, 2009).

Two females of *Paraphamartania stukei* Geller-Grimm, 1997 have been collected in Portugal, these being the first records of the species for this country. DNA barcoding of both new species and one specimen of *P. stukei* was successful and showed significant genetic divergence between both new species (5,4 % p-distance in the COI marker gene) with only little intraspecific distance (0,1%, 0,7%). A key is provided to all species of *Paraphamartania*.

KEY WORDS: Iberian Peninsula, *Aphamartania*, DNA barcoding, biogeography.

RESUMEN: Se recogieron ejemplares de dos especies sin describir del género *Paraphamartania* Engel, 1930, en España y Portugal en 2014 y 2015. Ambas especies son similares pero se pueden diferenciar fácilmente por caracteres de las alas, los esternitos, la genitalia y por métodos genéticos. Se vio claramente que algunos caracteres genéricos importantes que definen a *Paraphamartania*, como la espina apical de las tibias medias, habían pasado desapercibidos a anteriores autores y que la descripción actual del género está incompleta.

Un estudio comparativo de *Paraphamartania*, *Aphamartania* Schiner, 1866, and *Cophura* Osten Sacken, 1887, mostró que *Paraphamartania* era muy similar al género neártico *Cophura* sin caracteres claros que permitan diferenciarlos a excepción de la distribución geográfica. Por el contrario, *Paraphamartania* and *Cophura* pueden distinguirse fácilmente de *Aphamartania* o de cualquier otro género de la subfamilia Brachyrhopalinae (sensu DIKOW, 2009).

Dos ejemplares hembra de *Paraphamartania stukei* Geller-Grimm, 1997 fueron capturados en Portugal y constituyen las primeras citas de esta especie en dicho país. El estudio genético de las dos nuevas especies y de un ejemplar de *P. stukei* fue satisfactorio y mostró divergencia genética significativa entre las dos nuevas especies (5,4% de distancia en el gen marcador COI) con muy pequeña distancia intraespecífica (0,1%, 0,7%). Se proporciona una clave de identificación de todas las especies de *Paraphamartania*.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Península Ibérica, *Aphamartania*, DNA barcoding, biogeografía.

Introduction

Paraphamartania Engel, 1930, is a genus of asilid flies known only from the Palaearctic (Table 1). All species are rather small (body length up to 8.6 mm), with cell r_1 open, two-segmented maxillary palpi and antennal style and a specific chaetotaxy of the front legs (the foretibiae bear an apical s-shaped, bristle-like spur which is not situated on a process). MORTELMANS *et al.* (2014) revised the genus *Paraphamartania* and depicted all three known species: *Paraphamartania syriaca* (Schiner, 1867), *Paraphamartania stukei* Geller-Grimm, 1997 and *Paraphamartania marvaensis* Mortelmans, Tomasovic & Nagy, 2014.

Paraphamartania was proposed as a subgenus of *Aphamartania* Schiner, 1866 by ENGEL (1930) for *Aphamartania syriaca* (Schiner, 1867) and elevated to full generic status by PRITCHARD (1941).

In his original description of *A. syriaca*, Schiner stated that he had studied both male and female but failed to describe the genitalia. In 1930, Engel remarked that Schiner's type specimens in Vienna were both females. After comparison with the genus type material, *Aphamartania frauenfeldi* Schiner, 1866, Engel proposed the subgenus *Paraphamartania* for *A. syriaca*. He established some differences based on rather weak characters and took into account the difference in ecozones where the type specimens were collected: Neotropic and Palaearctic. Furthermore, he erroneously assumed that the male genitalia were similar to those of *Aphamartania* as we can read in the key to the Anthocneminae that he provided (ENGEL, 1930).

The male of *P. syriaca*, however, remained unknown until it was described by THEODOR (1980). Theodor noted that the male genitalia were rather small and rotated, very unlike those of *Aphamartania*, which has a large hypopygium bent forward under the abdomen (THEODOR, 1980; SCHINER, 1866). Probably on the basis of the Engel's false assumption, the North American taxonomist Pritchard neglected *Paraphamartania* and considered it a separate genus, thus elevating it to full generic status but without further justification (PRITCHARD, 1941). In his revision of *Annamyia* and *Aphamartania* (PRITCHARD, 1941) and later in his important revision of *Cophura* (PRITCHARD, 1943), Pritchard explicitly stated that he had not seen or studied any material of *Paraphamartania*. Since then, *Paraphamartania* has been accepted as a valid Palaearctic genus with a single species.

The taxonomic history of *Cophura* has been most troublesome. To start with, *Cophura* is a large, morphologically diverse genus, today known from at least 57 species. The genus has been described three times: as *Blax* (Loew, 1872), *Blacodes* (Loew, 1874) and *Loewiella* (Williston, 1896), all three names preoccupied and thus invalid. *Blax* is a junior primary homonym, preoccupied by Koch 1840, Thomson 1860 and Candeze 1863. *Blacodes* has the same status as *Blax*, preoccupied by Dejean 1859 and Blanchard 1845. For *Loewiella*, it was preoccupied by Meunier 1894. OSTEN SACKEN (1886) described *Cophura sodalis*; this was the first name that was not preoccupied and is now accepted as the valid name for the genus.

HINE (1908) pointed out the unreliable boundaries of the genus *Cophura* and suggested a critical study of sufficient material. BACK (1909) amplified his statement, describing *Cophura* as a repository for small asilids which bears clawlike spurs on their front tibiae. In the following years, several authors tried to revise this genus on the basis of a few species (e.g., CURRAN, 1923; MELANDER, 1924). Finally PRITCHARD

(1943) gave a more complete revision in which he examined more than 500 specimens and extended the range of his study to include South American species (no prior investigator had studied nor included the Palaearctic subgenus *Paraphamartania* in their revisions, stating that they had reviewed only Nearctic species).

The same held true for OSTEN SACKEN (1886): whilst describing *C. sodalis*, he wrote that he had not examined members of other genera such as *Blacodes* (= *Cophura*), so he erected a new genus for *C. sodalis* based on descriptions of *Blacodes* only. The authors assume that Osten Sacken neither saw nor studied *Aphamartania* (*Paraphamartania*). Then LOEW (1872; 1874), in publications on Nearctic Asilids, gave two brief genus descriptions for *Cophura* and was probably unaware of *Aphamartania syriaca* – a strict Palaearctic species. The same applies for WILLISTON (1908), who worked specifically on Nearctic material. None of these authors provided references as to which species they studied. The genotype of *Aphamartania* Schiner, *A. frauenfeldi*, is in a completely different genus than *Cophura* or *Paraphamartania* (see “Discussion”).

Material and methods

A series of specimens of two undescribed *Paraphamartania* species were collected from Portugal and Spain in 2014 and 2015, together with the first records of *P. stukei* for Portugal (see “Material studied” and Fig. 15-16). To study its congeners, the authors borrowed the holotype of *P. syriaca* from the Naturhistorisches Museum Wien (NHMW, Vienna) and 13 specimens of *P. syriaca* from the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences (RBINS, Brussels). The holotype of *P. stukei* was photographed in high resolution by the staff of the Staatliches Museum für Naturkunde Stuttgart (SMN, Stuttgart). The holotype of *P. marvaensis* was borrowed from the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences (RBINS, Brussels), while one paratype was still in care of the first author. Each four paratypes of *Cophura acapulcae* Pritchard, 1943 and *Cophura stylosa* Curran, 1931 were borrowed from the Smithsonian Institution (USNM, Washington). From Eric Fisher (Sacramento, USA) we received specimens of *Aphamartania frauenfeldi* Schiner, 1866, *Cophura feigei* Kaletta, 1983 and *Cophura wilcoxi* Kaletta, 1983 (see “Material studied”).

Morphological analyses and diagnoses of the specimens were performed with a Novex AR-Zoom stereomicroscope, with 40x magnification. Diagnoses of the male and female genitalia, general measurements and the photographs of the specimens were performed by use of a Leica M205 stereomicroscope, with up to 160x magnification. After identification, a middle leg from seven paratypes was removed for genetic analysis. We applied a DNA barcoding approach based on mitochondrial cytochrome oxidase I (COI) gene sequences. All details and protocols were the same as described in MORTELMANS *et al.* (2014). For a neighbour-joining tree reconstruction and for estimating genetic divergence, we used the software MEGA v6 (TAMURA *et al.*, 2013).

The following abbreviations for collectors and institutes are used in this paper: CAHE = Carlos Enrique Hermosilla Fernández; GRAG = Gregorio Aguado Arranz. JOAL = Jorge Mota Almeida; JOMO = Jonas Mortelmans; MNCN = Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid; NHM = Naturhistorisches Museum, Wien; NHML = Natural History Museum, London; NMNH = National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, Washington; OSAG = Luis Óscar Aguado Martín; PIAL = Piluca Álvarez Fidalgo; RBINS = Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Brussels; REVB = Reinoud van den Broek.

Results

Taxonomic accounts: Two new species of *Paraphamartania* are studied and photographed in high resolution.

Class Insecta Linnaeus, 1758
Order Diptera Linnaeus, 1758
Superfamily Asiloidea Latreille, 1802
Family Asilidae Latreille, 1802
Subfamily Brachyrhopalinae Dikow, 2009
Paraphamartania Engel, 1930

Paraphamartania Engel, 1930: 441.

Type species: *Aphamartania syriaca* (Schiner, 1867): 372-373.

Paraphamartania guadarramensis sp. nov.

Figs. 1-6 and 14

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:0F406B98-D9E7-4281-A5C2-1F594FEE9AA1

Diagnosis: A slender species with silvery greyish pubescence. Face slightly tinged silvery. Body and legs mainly black, margins of tergites, pleurae and legs tinged reddish, the reddish color being more pronounced in live specimens. Recognised by the spurs on the tips of fore-and-mid tibiae, the yellowish wing bases, and the brownish infuscated crossveins. Sternite 7 with a fringe of yellow-brown bristles and hairs. Aedeagal apodeme typical, in lateral view longer than high.

Fig. 1: *Paraphamartania guadarramensis* sp. nov. male in its natural habitat, Puerto de Navacerrada, Madrid, Spain, 30-VII-2014, (ÁLVAREZ, 2014).

<http://www.biodiversidadvirtual.org/insectarium/Paraphamartania-guadarramensis-Mortelmans-et-al.-2015-img621950.html>

<http://iberiandiptera.myspecies.info/species-list-and-info/paraphamartania-guadarramensis>

Type material of *Paraphamartania guadarramensis* sp. nov.

Holotype: SPAIN: Segovia, Pto. de Navacerrada, 40.791°N 4.009°W, 10-VII-2015, 1883 m, 1 ♂, leg. PIAL, col. RBINS reference nr. IG 33.148.

Paratypes: SPAIN: Segovia, Pto. de Navacerrada, 40.791°N 4.009°W, 1883 m, 10-VII-2015, 1 ♂, leg. OSAG, col. NHML, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, leg. GRAG, col. MNCN, 19-VII-2015, 1 ♂, abdomen dissected, leg. CAHE, col. NHML, 1 ♀, leg. OSAG, col. RBINS reference nr. IG 33.148; Segovia, Pto de Cotos, 40.817°N 3.965°W, 1912 m, 16-VII-2015, 1 ♀, leg. PIAL, col. REVB, 28-VII-2015, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, leg. GRAG, col. JOAL, 5-VIII-2015, 1 ♂, leg. OSAG, col. MNCN, 1 ♀, leg. OSAG, col. REVB.

Etymology: The species is named after the type locality: Sierra de Guadarrama, a mountain range forming the main eastern section of the system of mountain ranges at the center of the Iberian Peninsula.

This species was first detected in 2013 in Puerto de Navacerrada (Madrid province) (Fig. 14). A male was photographed recognizably for the first time in the same area on 30-VII-2014 (Fig. 1).

Fig. 2: *Paraphamartania guadarramensis* sp. nov. female in its natural habitat, Puerto de Navacerrada, Segovia, Spain, 19-VII-2015, (ÁLVAREZ, 2015).

<http://www.biodiversidadvirtual.org/insectarium/Paraphamartania-guadarramensis-Mortelmans-et-al.-2015-img754071.html>

<http://iberiandiptera.myspecies.info/species-list-and-info/paraphamartania-guadarramensis>

Description of *Paraphamartania guadarramensis* sp. nov.

Male (Figs. 1, 3-6):

- **Size:** Length 6.2 mm (excluding antennae), height of head 1 mm, width of head: 1.8 mm, length of antennae 0.9 mm, wing length 4.8 mm.
- **Head:** Black with face convex below antennae, head with heavy greyish pubescence. Mystax with fine, long, whitish hairs, with some larger bristles at mouth edge. Ocellar tubercle almost shiny with two long, brown, divergent ocellar bristles. Larger postocular setae white, slightly tinged yellow, smaller postocular setae entirely white. Hairs on face and frons white (Fig. 3).

Antennae located at one third from top of head, black with very light greyish pubescence. Scape and pedicel equal in length. Postpedicel four times as long as scape. Style two-segmented, second segment bearing an apical sensillum, style somewhat shorter than scape. Maxillary palpi and proboscis black with white setae. Maxillary palpi two-segmented.

Fig. 3: Male holotype *Paraphamartania guadarramensis* sp. nov. anterior view on head. Scale bar is 1 mm. (Photo: Jonas Mortelmans)

- **Thorax:** Ground colour black, scutum greyish pubescent. Postsutural area of scutum between suture and posterior end of scutum, on each side of the dorsocentral bristles, shiny and without pubescence. Presutural area of scutum, just in front of the suture to the posterior end of postpronotal lobe, on each side of the dorsocentral bristles, also shiny and without pubescence. These four areas are bordered by areas with heavier pubescence. Median line of scutum very narrow, heavily dusted, bordered by two lines of shinier areas (Fig. 4).
Short hairs on scutum white and evenly dispersed; other, longer hairs more yellowish. Two to three pairs of dorsocentral bristles, very small, barely longer than surrounding bristles, restricted to posterior side of scutum. Four to six weak presutural acrostichal bristles, no strong lateral postpronotal bristles, two strong notopleural bristles, two strong supra-alar bristles. All pleura black with greyish pubescence, without bristles except for the three to four white katatergal bristles. Halteres pale yellow, darker at base.
- **Scutellum:** Black, posteriorly shining black, anteriorly more dusted, with very, barely visible, small white to yellow discal scutellar setae. Marginal setae not present. Finely punctuated.
- **Legs:** Fore- and midfemora mainly black tinged reddish, much lighter in color than hind femora; apical tip of fore- and midfemora very light; hind femur black with apical tip, base and posterior side reddish-yellowish. Fore- and midtibiae very light in color, tinged reddish to yellowish; hind tibia black with base reddish-yellowish. Fore- and midtarsi much lighter in color than hind tarsus, bases of tarsal segments yellowish; hind tarsus black. All setae pale yellow, hairs and bristles whitish. Claws black with yellow base. Coxae black with white hairs, uniformly heavily greyish pubescent. Pulvilli present. Ventral tip of foretibia with large, black, S-shaped spine. Ventral tip of midtibia with two large, straight spines inserted very close to each other.
- **Wings:** Slightly brown infuscated all over, anterior and posterior crossveins more intensely infuscated. Base of wing yellowish. All veins brown. A small but distinctive white patch on the medius just basal to the discal cell. Anal cell petiolated, posterior cells and cell r_1 open. Alula hyaline, very small and rounded. Microtrichia present all over (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4: Male holotype *Paraphamartania guadarramensis* sp. nov. dorsal view. Scale bar is 1 mm. (Photo: Jonas Mortelmans)

Fig. 5: Male holotype *Paraphamartania guadarramensis* sp. nov. dorsal view of wing. Scale bar is 1 mm. (Photo: Jonas Mortelmans)

- **Male abdomen:** Shining black except for lateral margins of tergites 1-5, each of which has a narrow transverse band of greyish pubescence. Posterior edges of tergites 1-4 with dusting on lateral margin projected inward for a distance equal to one third the length of the lateral margin, the width of the inward projection about one fifth the length of the tergite. Tergites covered in both long and short whitish hairs, finely punctuated; abdomen as broad as thorax, barely narrowed towards posterior end (Fig. 4). Sternites heavily pubescent laterally, weakly pubescent centrally; hairs reddish except on sternites 5, 6 and 7, which have yellowish, more bristly, hairs. Sternite 7 with fringe of yellow-brown hair on hind edge.
- **Male terminalia:** Small, shiny black with yellowish setae; hypopygium rotated 45°; epandrium short; aedeagus conical with large apodeme and adeagal apodeme much longer than high (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: Male genitalia of paratype of *Paraphamartania guadarramensis* sp. nov. hypopygium in dorsal view. Scale bar is 500 μ m. (Photo: Jonas Mortelmans)

Female: Similar to male except tergites more reddish and dusting on tergites much broader and projected farther inwards (Fig. 2). Female terminalia: Tergites 8 and 9 form ovipositor; each acanthophorite bears three flattened, blunt spines.

Variation: The legs are variable in colour, but the femora are always black, sometimes with a dark reddish posterior side, very subtle. Femora often with reddish basal and apical tips; colour of tibiae especially variable, ranging from very dark to very reddish. The holotype male is a perfect intermediate form. In both males and females, tergal pubescence can range from almost no pubescence to very heavy pubescence.

DNA barcoding showed little (0,7%) intraspecific divergence among three paratypes.

Ecology: *P. guadarramensis* sp. nov. seems to dwell primarily in clearings in pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) woodlands, hunting at ground level on stony paths or resting on small stones and is active for most of July and August. It was observed preying on small flies.

Paraphamartania povoadaoensis sp. nov.

Figs. 7-11 and 15

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:A7F12593-D27B-43B3-8091-4D245D41E9F5

Diagnosis: Very similar to *P. guadarramensis* but in general somewhat stouter and larger. Face slightly tinged gold. Obvious differences are the very dark brown, infuscated wings, wing bases less yellow than those of *P. guadarramensis*, and 8th sternite with dark hairs and bristles rather than yellow-brownish hairs on *P. guadarramensis*. Terminalia differ only slightly, but lateral view of aedeagal apodeme is very different: short and circular in *P. povoadaoensis* and long and stretched in *P. guadarramensis*.

Fig. 7: *Paraphamartania povoadaoensis* sp. nov. female in its natural habitat, Póvoa Dão, Silgueiros, Viseu, Portugal, 31-VIII-2014, (ALMEIDA, 2015a).

<http://www.biodiversidadvirtual.org/insectarium/Paraphamartania-povoadaoensis-Mortelmans-et-al.-2015-img757898.html>

<http://iberiandiaptera.myspecies.info/species-list-and-info/paraphamartania-povoadaoensis>

Type material of *Paraphamartania povoadaoensis* sp. nov.

Holotype: PORTUGAL: Póvoa Dão - Silgueiros, Viseu, 40.546°N 7.946 °W, 13-IX-2014, 285 m, 1 ♂, n°21, leg. JOAL, col. RBINS reference nr. IG 33.148.

Paratypes: PORTUGAL: Beira Baixa Cast. Branco, Alameda, 40.008°N 7.662 °W, 8/10-IX-2009, 350 m, 1 ♂, leg. JOAL, Pires & Rodrigues, col. MNCN; Póvoa Dão - Silgueiros, Viseu, 40.546°N 7.946 °W, 10-VIII-2014, 285 m, 1 ♀, n° 1, leg. JOAL, col. NHML, 15-VIII-2014, 1 ♀, n° 3, leg. JOAL, col. NHML, 16-VIII-2014, 1 ♀, n° 2, leg. JOAL, col. JOMO, 30-VIII-2014, 2 ♂♂, n° 8 and 9, leg. JOAL, col. NHML, 4 ♀♀, n° 4, 6, 10 and 13, leg. JOAL, col. MNCN, 1 ♂, abdomen dissected, n° 7, leg. JOAL, col. NHML, 2 ♂♂, n° 11 and 12, leg. JOAL, col. JOMO, 1 ♀, n° 5, leg. JOAL, col. REVB, 31-VIII-2014, 2 ♀♀, n° 14 and 15, leg. JOAL, Col MNCN, 1 ♂, n° 16, leg. JOAL, col. MNCN, 13-IX-2014, 1 ♀, n° 17, leg. JOAL, col. NHML, 2 ♂♂, n° 18 and 19, leg. JOAL, col. MNCN, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, n° 20 and 23, leg. JOAL, col. JOAL, 1 ♂, n° 22, leg. JOAL, col. REVB, 1 ♀, n° 24, leg. JOAL, col. RBINS; Quinta da Abegoa, Marvão, 39.399°N 7.366°W, 25-VIII-2014, 600 m, 1 ♂, leg. JOAL, col. NHML.

Etymology: The species is named after the region in Portugal where most of the specimens were collected: Póvoa Dão.

Description of *Paraphamartania povoadaoensis* sp. nov.

Male (Figs. 8-11):

- **Size:** Length 7.5 mm (excluding antennae), height of head 1.2 mm, width of head 2 mm, length of antennae 1 mm, wing length 5.7 mm.
- **Head:** Black with face convex below antennae, head with heavy greyish pubescence. Mystax with fine, long, whitish hairs, some larger bristles only in lower part. Ocellar tubercle with greyish

pubescence, less dense than pubescence on frons with two long, brown, divergent ocellar bristles. Larger postocular setae white, slightly tinged yellow, smaller postocular setae all white. Hairs on face and frons white (Fig. 8).

Antennae located at one third from top of head, black with very light greyish pubescence. Scape and pedicel equal in length. Postpedicel four times as long as scape. Style two-segmented, second segment bearing an apical sensillum, style somewhat shorter than scape. Maxillary palpi and proboscis black with white setae. Maxillary palpi two-segmented.

Fig. 8: Male holotype *Paraphamartania povoadaoensis* sp. nov. anterior view on head. Scale bar is 1 mm. (Photo: Jonas Mortelmans)

- **Thorax:** Ground colour black, with grey pubescence. Postsutural area of scutum between suture and posterior end of scutum, on each side of the dorsocentral bristles, shiny and without pubescence. Presutural area of scutum, just in front of the suture to the posterior end of postpronotal lobe, on each side of the dorsocentral bristles, also shiny and without pubescence. These four areas are bordered by areas with heavier pubescence. Median line of scutum very narrow, heavily dusted, bordered by two lines of shinier areas (Fig 9).
Short hairs on scutum white and evenly dispersed; other, longer hairs more yellowish. Two to three pairs of dorsocentral bristles, very small, barely longer than surrounding bristles. Four to six weak presutural acrostichal bristles, no strong lateral postpronotal bristles, two strong notopleural bristles, two strong supra-alar bristles. All pleura black with greyish pubescence, without bristles except for the three to four white katatergal bristles. Halteres pale yellow, darker at base.
- **Scutellum:** Posteriorly shining black, anteriorly more dusted, with very, barely visible, small white to yellow discal scutellar setae. Marginal setae not present.
- **Legs:** Fore- and midfemora mainly black tinged reddish, much lighter in color than hind femora; apical tip of fore- and midfemora very light; hind femur black with apical tip, base and posterior side reddish-yellowish. Fore- and midtibiae very light in color, tinged reddish to yellowish; hind tibia black with base reddish-yellowish. Fore- and midtarsi much lighter in color than hind tarsus, bases of tarsal segments yellowish; hind tarsus black. All setae pale yellow, hairs and bristles whitish. Claws black with yellow base. Coxae black with white hairs, uniformly heavily greyish pubescent. Pulvilli present. Ventral tip of foretibia with black, S-shaped spine. Ventral tip of midtibia with two, straight spines inserted very close to each other.
- **Wings:** Heavily brown infuscated all over, anterior and posterior crossveins more intensely infuscated. Base of wing slightly yellowish. All veins brown. A small but distinctive white patch on

the medius just before the discal cell. Anal cell petiolate, posterior cells and r1 open. Alula very small, rounded and hyaline. Microtrichia present (Fig. 10).

Fig. 9: Male holotype *Paraphamartania povoadaoensis* sp. nov. dorsal view. Scale bar is 1 mm. (Photo: Jonas Mortelmans)

Fig. 10: Male holotype *Paraphamartania povoadaoensis* sp. nov. dorsal view of wing. Scale bar is 1 mm. (Photo: Jonas Mortelmans)

- **Male abdomen:** Shining black except for the lateral margins of tergites 1-5, each of which has a narrow transverse band of greyish pubescence. Posterior edges of tergites 1-4 with dusting on lateral margin projected inwards for a distance equal to one third the length of the lateral margin. The tergites are covered in both long and short whitish hairs and finely punctuated. The abdomen is as broad as the thorax, barely narrowed towards the posterior end of the abdomen (Fig. 9).

Sternites heavily pubescent laterally, weakly pubescent centrally. Hairs reddish except on sternites 5, 6 and 7, which have more bristly, darker hairs. Sternite 7 with tuft of blackish hair on hind edge.

- **Male terminalia:** Small, shiny black with yellowish setae; hypopygium rotated 45°, epandrium short; aedeagus conical with large apodeme, (Fig. 11). Aedagal apodeme short and circular.

Fig. 11: Male genitalia of paratype of *Paraphamartania povoadaoensis* sp. nov. hypopygium in dorsal view. (Photo: Jonas Mortelmans)

Female: Similar to male except tergites more reddish and dusting on tergites broader and projected farther inwards. Female terminalia: Tergite 8 and following are encapsulated in an ovipositor. Each acanthophorite bears three flattened, blunt spines.

Variation: The legs are variable in colour, but the femora are always black, sometimes with a dark reddish posterior side, very subtle. Femora often with reddish basal and apical tips; colour of tibiae especially variable, ranging from very dark to very reddish. In both males and females, tergal pubescence can range from almost no pubescence to very heavy pubescence. The golden shine on face and frons is sometime very weak but is always present when viewed from different angles.

DNA barcoding showed very little (0,1%) intraspecific divergence among paratypes from three localities.

Ecology: *P. povoadaoensis* sp. nov. was first detected in mid-August 2014 in Póvoa Dão (Fig. 14). The species seems to remain active until late September. It can be found perching on tips of *Retama* spp. and resting on stones or on the ground. It was observed to prey on hemipterans. *P. povoadaoensis* sp. nov. seems to inhabit clearings surrounded by *Pinus* spp., *Retama* sp., *Rubus* spp., or *Quercus* sp.

Key to Palaearctic *Paraphamartania* Engel, 1930

Although the male of *P. stukei* Geller-Grimm, 1997, is unknown, it is not unreasonable to think that males and females of this species are very much alike, as in its four related congeners. A key to all species of *Paraphamartania* is given below.

1a - Dorsocentral bristles very large, longest almost as long as height of head; wings clear but darker brown in the anterior basal half and slightly infuscated crossveins; marginal scutellar bristles present..... *P. syriaca* (Schiner, 1967). Male genitalia figs. 1 a-e, p. 213 in THEODOR (1980). Holotype pictured in plate 1: a-c in MORTELMANS *et al.* (2014).

- 1b** - Dorsocentral bristles small to absent; infuscation of wing variable, marginal scutellar bristles present or absent..... 2
- 2a** – Marginal scutellar bristles present; wings completely hyaline, with only posterior and anterior crossveins distinctly infuscated..... *P. marvaensis* Mortelmans, Tomasovic & Nagy, 2014. Holotype pictured in plate 1: d-f in MORTELMANS *et al.* (2014).
- 2b** - Marginal scutellar bristles absent, wings infuscation variable..... 3
- 3a** - Hind femora mainly bright reddish-yellow; wings darkened basally, apical part whitish..... *P. stukei* Geller-Grimm, 1997. Female holotype drawn in GELLER-GRIMM (1997), and holotype pictured in plate 1 g-f in MORTELMANS *et al.* (2014).
- 3b** - Hind femora black, often slightly lighter, but never bright reddish-yellow; wings hyaline to infuscated, if infuscated then infuscation never restricted to basal half 4
- 4a** - Sternite 7 with fringe of black hairs; wings very darkened; aedeagal apodeme small and semicircular; face and frons with subtle golden-grey pubescence, ocellar tubercle with golden-grey pubescence..... *P. povoadaoensis* sp. nov. Figs. 7-11.
- 4b** - Sternite 7 with fringe of yellow hairs, wings infuscated brown, mainly around crossveins; aedeagal apodeme long and stretched; face and frons with subtle silver-grey pubescence, ocellar tubercle shiny black.. *P. gadarramensis* sp. nov. Figs. 1-6.

Discussion

The taxonomic history of *Paraphamartania*, *Aphamartania* and *Cophura* has been complicated. A clear overview of their common history is discussed here.

Higher classification: At present, 16 genera of Brachyrhopalinae are known, formerly placed in the Isopogonini Hardy, 1948, (sensu PAPAVERO, 1973a; 1973b): *Alvarenga* Carrera, 1960, *Annamyia* Pritchard, 1941, *Aphamartania*, *Aspidopyga* Carrera, 1949, *Aterpogon* Hardy, 1930, *Comantella* Curran, 1923, *Cophura*, *Hodophylax* James, 1933, *Leptarthrus* Stephens, 1829, *Nerterhaptomenus* Hardy, 1934 *Nicocles* Jaenicke, 1867, *Omninablautus* Pritchard, 1935 *Paraphamartania*, *Questopogon* Dakin & Fordham, 1922 *Theurgus* Richter, 1966 and *Theromyia* Williston, 1891. Within this group, the presence or absence of pulvilli is a major feature to discriminate genera: the pulvilli can be reduced, absent or fully present. For further information HULL (1962) can be used.

Paraphamartania is similar to two Neotropical genera (*Aphamartania* and *Annamyia*) and one mainly Nearctic genus (*Cophura*). *Annamyia* can easily be distinguished by the unique foretarsi, which are greatly lengthened, twice as long as the anterior tibiae, and by the large and exposed genitalia (PRITCHARD, 1941). *Aphamartania* can be distinguished by means of a number of characters, listed in Table 1, but especially by the shape of the face below the eyes and the morphology of the hypopygium. Compared to related Palaearctic genera (*Theurgus* and *Leptarthrus*), *Paraphamartania* is easy to characterise on the basis of antennal characters, presence of acanthophorite spines and the hairs on the mesoscutum (MORTELMANS *et al.*, 2014). In contrast, *Cophura* cannot be easily distinguished from *Paraphamartania*; both genera lack clear characters by which they can be distinguished from each other.

<i>Aphamartania</i>	<i>Paraphamartania</i>	<i>Cophura</i>
Neotropic	Palaearctic	Nearctic+Neotropic
Antennae are located somewhat below the middle of the eyes	Antennae are located somewhat above the middle of the eyes	Antennae are located somewhat above the middle of the eyes
Only postsutural bristles (DC)	Presence or absence of presutural DC bristles	Presence or absence of presutural DC bristles
Back of head heavily haired.	Back of the head bare, with only a row of occipital macrosetae	Back of the head bare, with only a row of occipital macrosetae
A short, but heavy haired mystacal setae arranged in two tufts on the	Lack of a heavy, short haired mystacal setae	Lack of a heavy, short haired mystacal setae

sides of the medial line.		
Several strong bristles on hind edge of scutellum.	0-4 bristles on edge of scutellum	0-? bristles on edge of scutellum
Huge genitalia, well visible externally	Rather small genitalia, barely visible	Rather small genitalia, barely visible
The face widens below the antennae	The face is straight below the antennae	The face is straight below the antennae

Table 1: Differentiation of *Aphamartania* Schiner, 1866; *Paraphamartania* Engel, 1930, and *Cophura* Osten Sacken, 1887, by SCHINER (1867) and BROWN *et al.* (2010). Especially the widening of the face and the morphology of genitalia are useful characters.

Paraphamartania Engel, 1930: In the last two decades, four new species of *Paraphamartania* have been described, all from the Iberian Peninsula: *P. stukei*, *P. marvaensis*, *P. povoadaoensis* and *P. guadarramensis*. These four species reveal large intrageneric variation, especially the absence or presence of scutellar and dorsocentral bristles. Remarkably, these two characters can be found in the Nearctic genus *Cophura* (e.g., *Cophura daphne* Pritchard, 1943 which has striking dorsocentral bristles similar to *P. syriaca*, or another species groups of *Cophura* with or without scutellar bristles). The authors found no reliable characters for discriminating both genera, besides the geographic difference.

Characters of the species of *Cophura* and *Paraphamartania* that we studied seem to indicate a very close relationship between these genera. Strikingly similar are the structures of the terminalia (e.g., the bulbous apodeme, morphology of genitalia), cell r_1 open, two-segmented maxillary palpi, a two-segmented antennal style, the specific chaetotaxy of the front and mid tibiae, shape of the face and frons, variation of dorsocentral bristles and scutellar bristles and general morphology). A synonymy of both genera might well be possible. However, we think that many more species of *Cophura* should be examined and that both *Cophura* and *Paraphamartania* should be comprehensively studied and revised before any taxonomic conclusion is drawn. Many synapomorphies must be found only in these two genera and not in other Brachyrhopalinae (sensu DIKOW, 2009) to give sufficient evidence. We have chosen, therefore, to acknowledge the current status of *Paraphamartania*, although it seems that the only difference between the two genera lies in their geographical distribution (Nearctic/Neotropic vs. Palearctic).

Aphamartania Schiner, 1866: As described above, it is very unlikely that *Aphamartania* and *Cophura* are synonyms. These genera are easily distinguished from each other, supporting the conclusion that *Aphamartania* and *Paraphamartania* are two distinct genera.

Intrageneric discussion: *P. syriaca* is a poorly described species. The most striking error was made by SCHINER (1867), who stated that he studied a male and a female from Syria when in fact the type material (studied by Schiner and labelled by his hand) are two females. SCHINER (1867) provides neither details nor descriptions of male genitalia. The next error was made by ENGEL (1930), who provided a key to identify the genera of Acanthocneminae (sensu ENGEL). Strikingly, he did not succeed in keying out *Aphamartania* (subgen. *Paraphamartania*) appropriately: in the couplet between *Isopogon* (= *Leptarthrus*) and *Aphamartania* (subgen. *Paraphamartania*), he mentioned the presence or absence of spines on the tip of the midtibia, the shape of the mesonotum, the absence or presence of dorsocentral bristles, the presence or absence of acanthophorite spines (female), and the large hypopygium of *Aphamartania* (*Paraphamartania*). At least two of these characters are incorrect: *Paraphamartania* does have a spine on the tip of the midtibia, and *Paraphamartania* does not have a large hypopygium. Strangely, all known specimens of *P. syriaca* at that time were females. ENGEL (1930) was correct in stating that the type material of *P. syriaca* consisted of two females from Syria, so the question that must be asked is how he could comment on the hypopygium. It was THEODOR (1980) who first described the small, concealed genitalia of *P. syriaca*.

Most important publications on *Paraphamartania* -SCHINER (1867), ENGEL (1930), GELLER-GRIMM (1997) and MORTELMANS (2014)- do not mention the presence of a spine on the tip of the midtibia. Here, examination of type material of all *Paraphamartania* showed that all currently known species do have this feature, which is shared widely amongst the several Brachyrhopalinae genera (e.g. *Aphamartania*, *Aspidopyga*, *Cophura*, *Leptarthrus*, *Theurgus*.) (Fig. 13). Although Richter and Lehr, whilst describing *Theurgus zimini* Lehr, 1974 and *Theurgus kerzneri* RICHTER, 1966 respectively, did not mention this

character, it is actually there: RICHTER & ASTAKOV (2012) revised holotypes of both species of *Theurgus* and confirmed the presence of this spine.

Fig. 12: COI-Neighbor joining tree representing species of *Paraphamartania* Engel, 1930, and *Cophura* Osten Sacken, 1887, rooted with *Dioctria* (Diptera: Asilidae). Bootstrap support was estimated with 2000 replicates.

Fig. 13: Tip of tibiae one (right) and tibiae two (left), anterior view (paratype of *Cophura acapulcae*, Pritchard, 1943). (Photo: Jonas Mortelmans)

Conclusions

Two very similar but distinguishable new species of *Paraphamartania* emphasise the remarkable asilid fauna found on the Iberian Peninsula.

Nearctic taxonomists have been neglecting *Paraphamartania* since the description of *P. syriaca* due to the erroneous descriptions by ENGEL (1930), who stated *Paraphamartania* has a big hypopygium like *Aphamartania*, while only females were known at that time. SCHINER (1867) described a couple from Syria while he was in fact looking at two females, and OSTEN SACKEN (1886), LOEW (1872; 1874) and WILLISTON (1896) all described *Cophura* independently without seeing type material of *Paraphamartania*. All of this led to the false assumption that *Paraphamartania* is similar to *Aphamartania*, confusing later

taxonomists like PRITCHARD (1941; 1943). Furthermore, all researchers so far did not report on the obvious spines on the tip of tibia 2 of *Paraphamartania*, a character shared with e.g. *Cophura*.

In this study, albeit with limited type material, it is clear that *Paraphamartania* and *Cophura* are closely related genera (morphology of terminalia, cell r_1 open, two-segmented maxillary palpi, a two-segmented antennal style, the specific chaetotaxy of the front and mid legs, shape of the face and frons, location of the antennae, variation of dorsocentral bristles and scutellar bristles and general morphology). Although the authors currently accept *Paraphamartania* as a valid genus, we hope to encourage taxonomists having access to *Cophura* type specimens, to study and compare *Paraphamartania*.

Further material studied

***Paraphamartania marvaensis* Mortelmans, Tomasovic & Nagy, 2014:** 1 ♂, 6-IV-2013, Portugal, Marvão, 39.39727° N, 7.364521° W, leg. det. JOMO, col. RBINS, holotype; 1 ♂, 1 ♀; Portugal, Marvão, 6-IV-2013, 39.39727° N, 7.364521° W, leg. det. JOMO, col. RBINS, paratype; 1 ♂, 6-IV-2013, Portugal, Marvão, 39.39727° N, 7.364521° W, leg. det. JOMO, col. JOMO, paratype; 2 ♀♀, 14-III-2015, Portugal, Quinta da Abegoa – Marvão, leg. det. Ana Gonçalves, Rui Andrade, JOAL, col. JOAL.

***Paraphamartania syriaca* Schiner, 1867:** 2 ♀♀, no date, Gödl, Syria, leg. det. Schiner, col. NHMW, holotype.

***Cophura feigei* Kaletta, 1983:** 1 ♂, 1 ♀, 21-II-1966, Venezuela, Edo. Miranda - San Ant. de los Altos: Los Moralitos, 900 m, leg. José Manuel Ayala L., col. JOAL, paratypes.

***Cophura wilcoxi* Kaletta, 1983:** 1 ♀, XII-1976, Venezuela, Guarico - San Francisco de Tiznados. - Hda. Carrizalito – Palambrota, leg. L. Plaza Ayala, col. JOAL, paratype; 1 ♂, I-1976, Venezuela, Guarico - San Francisco de Tiznados. - Hda. Carrizalito – Palambrota; leg. L. Plaza Ayala, col. JOAL, paratype.

***Cophura acapulcae* Pritchard, 1943:** 1 ♂, 9-VI-1935, México, Acapulco, Gro. leg. det. A.E. Pritchard, col. NMNH. ; 2 ♀♀, 11-VI-1935, México, Acapulco, Gro. leg. det. A.E. Pritchard, col. NMNH, paratype; 1 ♂, 11-VI-1935, México, Acapulco, Gro. leg. det. A.E. Pritchard. col. NMNH, paratype.

***Cophura stylosa* Curran, 1931:** 2 ♂♂ 2 ♀♀, 10-VII-1934, Boise City, Oklahoma, leg. det. A.E. Pritchard, col. NMNH.

***Aphamartania frauenfeldi* Schiner, 1866:** 1 ♀, 22-V-1980, Venezuela Edo. Aragua - P. N. Henry Pittier – Mirador, 900 m, leg. det. José Manuel Ayala, col. JOAL; 1 ♂, 22-III-1975, Venezuela, Edo. Aragua - P. N. Henry Pittier – Mirador, 200 m, leg. det. José Manuel Ayala, col. JOAL.

***Paraphamartania stukei* Geller-Grimm, 1997:** 1 ♀, 9-VI-2011, Portugal, Nave de Santo António - Serra da Estrela, ca. 1500m, leg. JOAL, det. Eric Fisher, col. JOAL; 1 ♀, 7-VI-2011, Portugal, Póvoa Dão - Silgueiros – Viseu, leg. JOAL, det. Eric Fisher, col. JOAL.

Fig. 14: Distribution of *Paraphamartania guadarramensis* sp. nov. (●) and *Paraphamartania povoadaoensis* sp. nov. (★) based of holotypes and paratypes localization.

Fig. 15: Known world distribution of *Paraphamartania stukei* Geller-Grimm, 1997 (■) and new records in Portugal (★) based on “Further material studied” data.

Fig. 16: *Paraphamartania stukei* Geller-Grimm, 1997, female in its natural habitat, Póvoa Dão, Silgueiros, Viseu, Portugal, 7-VI-2011, (ALMEIDA, 2015b)

<http://www.biodiversidadvirtual.org/insectarium/Paraphamartania-stukei-Geller-Grimm-1997-img757892.html>

<http://iberiandiaptera.myspecies.info/species-list-and-info/paraphamartania-stukei>

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